

checkCIF/PLATON report

Structure factors have been supplied for datablock(s) AP_R10_prop_Sq_Cyt_RT

THIS REPORT IS FOR GUIDANCE ONLY. IF USED AS PART OF A REVIEW PROCEDURE FOR PUBLICATION, IT SHOULD NOT REPLACE THE EXPERTISE OF AN EXPERIENCED CRYSTALLOGRAPHIC REFEREE.

No syntax errors found. CIF dictionary Interpreting this report

Datablock: AP_R10_prop_Sq_Cyt_RT

Bond precision: C-C = 0.0042 A Wavelength=0.71073

Cell: a=8.2405 (3) b=12.6825 (5) c=16.3143 (7)
 alpha=90 beta=90 gamma=90

Temperature: 295 K

	Calculated	Reported
Volume	1705.01 (12)	1705.01 (12)
Space group	P 21 21 21	P 21 21 21
Hall group	P 2ac 2ab	P 2ac 2ab
Moiety formula	C18 H17 N3 O3, H2 O	C18 H17 N3 O3, H2 O
Sum formula	C18 H19 N3 O4	C18 H19 N3 O4
Mr	341.36	341.36
Dx, g cm ⁻³	1.330	1.330
Z	4	4
Mu (mm ⁻¹)	0.096	0.096
F000	720.0	720.0
F000'	720.34	
h, k, lmax	11, 17, 22	11, 17, 22
Nref	4682 [2662]	4143
Tmin, Tmax	0.974, 0.986	0.979, 1.000
Tmin'	0.974	

Correction method= # Reported T Limits: Tmin=0.979 Tmax=1.000
AbsCorr = MULTI-SCAN

Data completeness= 1.56/0.88 Theta(max)= 29.312

R(reflections)= 0.0481 (2642)

wR2(reflections)=
0.1067 (4143)

S = 1.033

Npar= 230

The following ALERTS were generated. Each ALERT has the format

test-name_ALERT_alert-type_alert-level.

Click on the hyperlinks for more details of the test.

Alert level C

PLAT340_ALERT_3_C Low Bond Precision on C-C Bonds 0.00419 Ang.

Alert level G

PLAT007_ALERT_5_G Number of Unrefined Donor-H Atoms 3 Report
H18 H1WA H1WB

PLAT032_ALERT_4_G Std. Uncertainty on Flack Parameter Value High . 0.300 Report

PLAT720_ALERT_4_G Number of Unusual/Non-Standard Labels 2 Note
H1WA H1WB

PLAT791_ALERT_4_G Model has Chirality at C1 (Sohncke SpGr) S Verify

PLAT791_ALERT_4_G Model has Chirality at C5 (Sohncke SpGr) S Verify

PLAT899_ALERT_4_G SHELXL2018 is Outdated and Succeeded by SHELXL 2019/3 Note

PLAT910_ALERT_3_G Missing # of FCF Reflection(s) Below Theta(Min). 2 Note
0 1 1, 0 0 2,

PLAT912_ALERT_4_G Missing # of FCF Reflections Above STh/L= 0.600 202 Note

PLAT916_ALERT_2_G Hooft y and Flack x Parameter Values Differ by . 0.20 Check

PLAT969_ALERT_5_G The 'Henn et al.' R-Factor-gap value 3.261 Note
Predicted wR2: Based on SigI**2 3.27 or SHELX Weight 10.33

PLAT978_ALERT_2_G Number C-C Bonds with Positive Residual Density. 0 Info

- 0 **ALERT level A** = Most likely a serious problem - resolve or explain
- 0 **ALERT level B** = A potentially serious problem, consider carefully
- 1 **ALERT level C** = Check. Ensure it is not caused by an omission or oversight
- 11 **ALERT level G** = General information/check it is not something unexpected

- 0 ALERT type 1 CIF construction/syntax error, inconsistent or missing data
- 2 ALERT type 2 Indicator that the structure model may be wrong or deficient
- 2 ALERT type 3 Indicator that the structure quality may be low
- 6 ALERT type 4 Improvement, methodology, query or suggestion
- 2 ALERT type 5 Informative message, check
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It is advisable to attempt to resolve as many as possible of the alerts in all categories. Often the minor alerts point to easily fixed oversights, errors and omissions in your CIF or refinement strategy, so attention to these fine details can be worthwhile. In order to resolve some of the more serious problems it may be necessary to carry out additional measurements or structure refinements. However, the purpose of your study may justify the reported deviations and the more serious of these should normally be commented upon in the discussion or experimental section of a paper or in the "special_details" fields of the CIF. checkCIF was carefully designed to identify outliers and unusual parameters, but every test has its limitations and alerts that are not important in a particular case may appear. Conversely, the absence of alerts does not guarantee there are no aspects of the results needing attention. It is up to the individual to critically assess their own results and, if necessary, seek expert advice.

Publication of your CIF in IUCr journals

A basic structural check has been run on your CIF. These basic checks will be run on all CIFs submitted for publication in IUCr journals (*Acta Crystallographica*, *Journal of Applied Crystallography*, *Journal of Synchrotron Radiation*); however, if you intend to submit to *Acta Crystallographica Section C* or *E* or *IUCrData*, you should make sure that full publication checks are run on the final version of your CIF prior to submission.

Publication of your CIF in other journals

Please refer to the *Notes for Authors* of the relevant journal for any special instructions relating to CIF submission.

